

**SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE, STRESS LEVEL AND
DEPRESSION AMONG ADOLESCENTS**

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Abstract

Introduction: A person of any religious persuasion can benefit from developing their intrinsic spiritual intelligence (SQ).

Methods: The aim of the study was to examine the spiritual intelligence, stress level, and level of depression among Junior High School students. Using stratified sampling in each grade level, 389 students from two Junior High Schools in Licab District were selected to participate in the study. Each participant was required to complete three standardized tests, including Spiritual Intelligence Self Report Inventory (SISRI-24), Perceived Stress Scale, and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). Descriptive correlational statistics were used to identify the correlation and significance of the variables to each other, utilizing Pearson's R.

Results: The results revealed that there is a correlation between the stress level and spiritual intelligence of the students, although it is not strongly correlated. This means that the higher the stress the students experience, the higher the level of spiritual intelligence they exhibit. In contrast, the analysis showed that there is no correlation between spiritual intelligence and depression, indicating that the level of spiritual intelligence does not affect or is not related to the level of depression among the students.

Conclusions: Lastly, the findings revealed that the students' perceived stress level is strongly correlated with their level of depression. In other words, students who experience higher levels of stress may exhibit higher levels of depression.

Keywords: Spiritual Intelligence, Correlation, Depression, Stress, Junior High School Students, Basic Education

Introduction

There is increasing worry for the mental health and well-being of today's youth because of the many pressures they confront. This study explored the correlation between spirituality and mental health since the researcher was exposed to these issues in the course of his work as a preacher and public-school teacher. Recently, talks about spiritual intelligence, also known as spiritual quotient (SQ), have gained traction in the fields of science and psychology. It's a kind of intelligence that aids people in comprehending the significance of their experiences, gaining a broader perspective on life, and weighing the pros and cons of potential courses of action. The integration of logical and emotional reasoning requires SQ, as proved by research.

Spiritual intelligence (SQ) is a concept that can be experienced by anyone as an innate capability without relying on religious beliefs. It is based on the science of the soul and represents secular spirituality. According to Haugen (2018), spiritual intelligence refers to an individual's capacity to ask questions about the ultimate meaning of life and the relationship between oneself and the world. It leads to an increase in psychological well-being and provides a sense of purpose in life. Spiritual intelligence is the result of the highest level of individual growth in cognition, meaning attainment, transcendental and moral communication (Alrashidi et al., 2022).

SQ goes beyond an individual's physical and cognitive relationship with the environment and addresses matters of ultimate concern, values, meaning, and purpose. It helps individuals recognize and employ their higher self over their ego to solve problems with compassion, wisdom, and equanimity. Atroszko et al., (2021) describes spiritual intelligence as a set of mental capacities that contribute to awareness, integration, and adaptive application of non-material and transcendent aspects of one's existence, leading to outcomes such as deep existential reflection, enhancement of meaning, recognition of a transcendent self, and mastery of spiritual states. SQ integrates other intelligences, activates creativity, and discloses our relationship with the world, which produces products and outcomes for the well-being of all people, all beings, and the planet (Skrzypinska, 2021).

As a time of fast physical and mental development, adolescence is sometimes referred to as a "storm and stress" time. Students may be expected to deal with stressful conditions and remain resilient despite a lack of coping mechanisms and awareness of the risks involved because of the emphasis on academic performance. Consequently, the purpose of this dissertation is to explore the connection between spiritual intelligence and the emotional difficulties that Filipino high school students have. This study's results have the potential to illuminate the value of SQ as an intervention for addressing mental health issues including stress and depression in young people and pave the way for additional studies on the link between SQ and other mental health issues.

In sum, the purpose of this study is to add to the expanding body of research on the connection between spiritual intelligence and mental health in young people. This study has the potential to offer insight on the role of spiritual intelligence as an intervention in promoting mental health and well-being among adolescents by examining the association between SQ and stress and depression in high school students in the Filipino environment. This study's findings may also be relevant to other efforts to better the mental health of young people through the design of interventions and programs.

Research Questions

The research aimed to study the relationship between spiritual intelligence, depression, and perceived stress among adolescents, specifically junior high school students from Grades 7 to 10 of Licab District. The research questions were divided into two categories: descriptive questions and inferential questions. The descriptive questions focused on the respondents' profile, while the inferential questions explored the relationships between the variables of interest. The study aimed to identify the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, religion, and birth order, as well as describe their spiritual intelligence, level of depression, and level of stress. The inferential questions aimed to determine the significant relationships between the respondents' profile and their spiritual intelligence, level of depression, and level of stress. Additionally, the study aimed to identify the relationship between spiritual intelligence and depression, spiritual intelligence and stress, and depression and stress.

Methods

Research Design: The study employed a descriptive correlational statistic design to investigate the relationships between spiritual intelligence, stress, and depression among junior high school students.

Sample and Sampling Procedure: Participants were chosen using a stratified selection procedure from a group of 1,331 eighth graders. The sample includes 658 male and 673 female students from grades 7-10 at both institutions. Population, grade level, gender, and sample size all had a role in determining the size of the representative sample. Nueva Ecija, Philippines' Exequiel R. Lina and Sta. Maria National High Schools hosted the research.

Data Gathering Tools/Instrumentation: The research used three standardized tests: the Spiritual Intelligence Self-Report Inventory (SISRI-24) to measure spiritual intelligence, the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) to screen for depression, and the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) to assess perceived stress. Validation and reliability of these instruments were conducted by their respective developers.

Data Analysis: Pearson's r test was used to test mean differences. The scores of each test were computed, with reversed items noted for SISRI-24 and PSS. The total score was obtained for each test, and severity of symptoms was noted for BDI.

Results

Profile of Respondents. This study profiled 389 pupils from two Licab District Junior High Schools. Gender, birth order, grade level, and religion were requested. Females outnumbered males 50.10% to 49.10%. Born Again (8.70%), Iglesia ni Cristo (3.30%), Baptist (3.90%), Islam (0.50%), and Jehovah's Witness (0.30%) followed Roman Catholic (83.30%). Most responders (36%) were first-born.

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents (n=389)

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Age	11	1	0.30
	12	66	17.00
	13	103	26.50
	14	95	24.40
	15	86	22.10
	16	38	9.80
Gender	Female	195	50.10
	Male	194	49.10
Religion	Roman Catholic	324	83.30
	Born Again	34	8.70
	Iglesia ni Cristo	13	3.30
	Baptist	15	3.90
	Islam	2	0.50
	Jehovah's Witness	1	0.30
Birth Order	First	140	36.00
	Second	109	28.00
	Third	76	19.50
	Fourth	29	7.50
	Fifth	17	4.40
	Sixth	9	2.30
	Seventh	6	1.50
	Ninth	2	0.50
	Twelveth	1	0.30

Spiritual Intelligence. This study aimed to assess the spiritual intelligence of Junior High School students in Licab District using Kings' Spiritual Intelligence Inventory Report (SISIRI-24). The results showed that 26.22% of the respondents had a high level of spiritual intelligence, while 64.78% were categorized as moderate and 9% had low spiritual intelligence. The mean spiritual intelligence score was 56.29, indicating a moderate level of spiritual intelligence among the participants.

Table 2. Students Spiritual Intelligence

Spiritual Intelligence	Frequency	Percentage
65-96 (High)	102	26.22
40-64 Moderate	252	64.78
0-39 (Low)	35	9.00
Total	389	100.00
Mean Spiritual Intelligence:	56.29	(Moderate)

Depression Inventory. The results showed that 143 (36.76%) respondents had a score indicating moderate depression, while 91 (23.49%) and 77 (19.79%) were classified as having mild mood disturbance and borderline clinical depression, respectively. Only 33 (8.48%) respondents had normal scores on the BDI. Five students (1.29%) had extreme depression, and the mean depression score was 20.53, indicating moderate depression.

Table 3 Results of the Students' Depression Inventory

Depression	F	%
1 - 10 (Normal)	33	8.48
11 - 16 (Mild mood disturbance)	91	23.39
17 - 20 (Borderline clinical depression)	77	19.79
21 - 30 (Moderate depression)	143	36.76
31 - 40 (Severe depression)	40	10.28
over 40 (Extreme depression)	5	1.29
Total	389	100.00
Mean Depression: 20.53 (Moderate depression)		

Perceived Stress Level. This study aimed to assess the perceived stress level of Junior High School students in Licab District. The results revealed that the mean perceived stress score was 20.16, indicating a moderate level of stress among the sample population. Most respondents (90.75%) had scores ranging from 14 to 26, indicating moderate stress levels. A small proportion of respondents (3.34%) reported low stress levels, while 5.91% were perceived to have high levels of stress.

Table 4. PSS Scores of the Respondents

Stress	Frequency	Percentage
0 - 13	13	3.34
14 - 26	353	90.75
27 - 40	23	5.91
Total	389	100.00

*Scores ranging from 0-13 would be considered low stress, 14-26 moderate stress. 27-40 high perceived stress

Correlation of Profile, Depression, Stress and Spiritual Intelligence. Table 5 presents the correlation and significance of the respondents' profile, including age, sex, religion, birth order, and grade level, with their levels of depression, perceived stress, and spiritual intelligence. The table shows the correlation coefficient values and the significance levels (2-tailed) of each variable pair.

Table 5 Correlation and Significance of Profile, Depression, Stress and Spiritual Intelligence

Profile		Depression	Stress	SI
Age	Correlation Coefficient	-.144**	.135**	.140**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.004	0.008	0.006
Sex	Correlation Coefficient	0.003	0.063	-0.124*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.959	0.218	0.014
Religion	Correlation Coefficient	-0.076	0.045	-0.053
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.136	0.372	0.943
Birth Order	Correlation Coefficient	0.028	-0.08	-0.073
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.577	0.116	0.375
Grade	Correlation Coefficient	-.157**	.146**	.155**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.002	0.004	0.002
**.		Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).		N= 389

The results indicate a significant negative correlation between age and depression, stress, and spiritual intelligence, with correlation coefficients of -.144**, .135**, and .140**, respectively. This suggests that as age increases, the levels of depression, stress, and spiritual intelligence tend to decrease. Sex was found to be significantly correlated with spiritual intelligence, with a correlation coefficient of -0.124*. This indicates that female respondents tend to have higher levels of spiritual intelligence than male respondents.

Religion and birth order did not show a significant correlation with depression, stress, or spiritual intelligence. The correlation coefficients were all close to zero, with insignificant p-values. Grade level was significantly correlated with depression, stress, and spiritual intelligence, with correlation coefficients of -.157**, .146**, and .155**, respectively. This suggests that as grade level increases, the levels of depression, stress, and spiritual intelligence tend to decrease.

Discussions

Profile of Respondents. The profile of the respondents in this study provides important insights into the characteristics of the sample population. Most of the respondents were between the ages of 12 to 15, which is consistent with the target age range of junior high school students. The gender distribution was almost equal, with females slightly outnumbering males. This indicates that the study was able to recruit a representative sample of the junior high school student population in the Licab District.

In terms of religion, Roman Catholics comprised most of the respondents at 83.30%. The relatively small percentages of Born Again, Iglesia ni Cristo, Baptist, Islam, and Jehovah's Witness suggest that the study may have had limited representation from students of other religions. It is important to consider the potential influence of religious beliefs on the variables being studied, such as depression, stress, and spiritual intelligence. Birth order was also an important profile characteristic of the respondents. Most of the respondents were first-borns, comprising 36% of the sample. This information may provide insights into potential family dynamics and how they may impact the variables being studied. For example, first-borns may experience higher levels of stress due to parental pressure and expectations.

Overall, the profile of the respondents is an important aspect of the study as it helps contextualize the results and provides insights into potential factors that may be influencing the variables being studied.

It is important to consider the potential limitations of the sample population and to ensure that the results are not overgeneralized to the larger population without careful consideration of the profile characteristics of the respondents.

Spiritual Intelligence. The findings of this study on the spiritual intelligence of junior high school students in Licab District have significant implications for educators, parents, and policymakers. The results indicate that a considerable proportion of the students have moderate levels of spiritual intelligence, highlighting the need to recognize this aspect of their development. It is worth noting that spiritual intelligence goes beyond religious beliefs and includes a range of qualities such as compassion, empathy, and self-awareness.

The fact that over a quarter of the students had high levels of spiritual intelligence is a positive finding, suggesting that there is potential for spiritual growth among these students. Educators and parents can focus on nurturing the spiritual development of these students to help them become well-rounded individuals who can cope with life's challenges with resilience and equanimity. Many students were categorized as having moderate levels of spiritual intelligence, indicating that there is an opportunity to enhance their spiritual development. Targeted interventions such as mindfulness practices, reflective writing, and service-learning projects that foster compassion and empathy can help these students develop their spiritual intelligence.

The group of students categorized as having low levels of spiritual intelligence require special attention from educators and parents. These students may need additional support and guidance to develop their spiritual intelligence and address any underlying psychological issues that may be hindering their growth. Overall, this study highlights the importance of addressing spiritual intelligence as a key aspect of students' development. By recognizing the significance of spiritual intelligence, educators and parents can provide a holistic education that addresses the cognitive, emotional, and spiritual dimensions of students' lives (Zainal-Abidin et al., 2018).

Depression Inventory. The results of this study on the depression inventory of junior high school students in Licab District reveal the importance of addressing mental health issues among young people. Depression can have a significant impact on students' academic performance, social interactions, and overall well-being. As such, it is crucial for educators, parents, and mental health professionals to work together to identify and address depression early on. The findings indicate that a significant proportion of students in Licab District are experiencing moderate to severe levels of depression, highlighting the need for increased awareness and intervention. Educators and parents can play a vital role in identifying the underlying causes of depression and providing support to students to help them overcome it.

The study also highlights the importance of targeted interventions for students with mild mood disturbance and borderline clinical depression. Cognitive-behavioral therapy or group counseling can help these students develop coping skills and improve their mental well-being (Carpena et al., 2023). Even students with normal scores on the BDI can benefit from learning resilience-building techniques and strategies to help them maintain their mental health and well-being. Overall, this study underscores the need for increased attention to mental health issues among junior high school students. By addressing depression early on and providing targeted interventions and support, educators and parents can help students develop the resilience and coping skills they need to thrive both in and outside of the classroom (Khalid, 2019).

Perceived Stress Level. This study sheds light on the perceived stress levels of junior high school students in Licab District, providing important insights for educators, parents, and mental health professionals. The findings suggest that a significant proportion of students experience moderate levels of stress, which may have negative impacts on their physical and mental health, academic performance, and social relationships. Therefore, it is essential to identify and address the underlying causes of stress to promote the well-being of students (Van Loon et al., 2019).

The results also highlight the need for tailored interventions that match the varying levels of stress among students. While most students experience moderate stress levels, a small proportion have low stress levels, and some may have effective coping mechanisms. These findings suggest that interventions should be targeted, addressing the specific needs of individual students. Finally, the study emphasizes the importance of early detection and intervention in addressing perceived stress levels among students.

Educators and parents can play a crucial role in identifying the symptoms of stress and implementing appropriate interventions, such as stress management techniques, mindfulness practices, and counseling (Di Bratto, 2020). Most importantly, this study provides valuable insights into the perceived stress levels of junior high school students in Licab District, highlighting the need for increased attention to the mental health and well-being of students. As highlighted in the study of Chue & Cheung (2023), recognizing the significance of perceived stress levels, and addressing them early on, educators, parents, and mental health professionals can help students develop the resilience and coping skills they need to thrive both in and outside of the classroom.

Correlation of Profile, Depression, Stress and Spiritual Intelligence. The findings of this study have significant implications for understanding the relationship between profile factors and mental health outcomes among junior high school students. The significant negative correlation between age and depression, stress, and spiritual intelligence implies that younger students are more prone to experiencing depression and stress compared to their older counterparts. This suggests the need for early intervention and prevention strategies to address mental health issues among junior high school students, particularly among younger students (Francis et al., 2021).

The significant correlation between sex and spiritual intelligence indicates that female students tend to have higher levels of spiritual intelligence than male students. This finding highlights the potential importance of incorporating spiritual and religious practices in mental health interventions for junior high school students, particularly for male students who may be more likely to experience lower levels of spiritual intelligence (Raina, 2018).

The lack of significant correlation between religion and birth order with mental health outcomes suggests that these factors may not have a direct impact on depression, stress, or spiritual intelligence among junior high school students. However, it is still important to consider these factors when designing mental health interventions as they may still have indirect effects on mental health outcomes (Megalakaki & Kokou-Kpolou, 2022).

Finally, the significant negative correlation between grade level and depression, stress, and spiritual intelligence suggests that students tend to experience lower levels of mental health issues as they progress through junior high school. This highlights the potential importance of providing mental health support for younger students, particularly those in lower grades, to prevent and address mental health issues before they become more severe (Hermann-Werner et al., 2022). Overall, the findings of this study provide important insights into the relationship between profile factors and mental health outcomes among junior high school students, which can inform the development of effective mental health interventions in this population.

Conclusions

This study provides important insights into the mental health and well-being of junior high school students in Licab District. The study findings highlight the need for increased attention to mental health issues among students, particularly with regards to depression, perceived stress levels, and spiritual intelligence. The study also provides valuable insights into the potential influence of demographic and profile factors on mental health outcomes, such as age, sex, religion, and birth order. These findings can inform the development of tailored interventions and prevention strategies to address mental health issues among junior high school students. Overall, this research study underscores the importance of a holistic approach to education that addresses the cognitive, emotional, and spiritual dimensions of students' lives to promote their overall well-being and development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made for educators, parents, and mental health professionals to promote the well-being and development of junior high school students in Licab District. Firstly, educators and parents should recognize the importance of addressing spiritual intelligence as a key aspect of students' development and focus on nurturing the spiritual growth of students with low to moderate levels of spiritual intelligence through targeted interventions such as mindfulness

practices, reflective writing, and service-learning projects. Additionally, mental health issues such as depression and perceived stress levels should be identified and addressed early on through targeted interventions such as cognitive-behavioral therapy, group counseling, stress management techniques, mindfulness practices, and counseling. Furthermore, educators and mental health professionals should consider the potential influence of profile factors such as age, gender, religion, and birth order when designing mental health interventions for junior high school students. By recognizing the significance of these profile factors, they can provide more effective and tailored interventions to address mental health issues among this population. Overall, this study highlights the need for increased attention and support to promote the mental health and well-being of junior high school students in Licab District.

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